

THE TYPES AND MAIN PRINCIPLES OF COACHING

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Abstract. *This paper shows that the most effective principles of coaching. The coaching process harmoniously combines two principles: the principle of awareness and the principle of responsibility. If a person follows the principles of coaching, then he will feel free. And freedom is manifested only when a person is aware of his desires and aspirations; when he determines where he is on the way to the realization of his goal, when he chooses his only path from the whole variety of indicated paths and begins to act on the basis of the plan he has developed to achieve a specific result.*

Keywords: *coaching, client, individual, staff, personal, corporate, good choice, positive desire, confidentiality, motive, disposition, flexibility, hierarchization, responsibility, aggressive hopelessness, regressive hopelessness, self-blame.*

Introduction. Coaching works at the level of consciousness and serves to expand the boundaries of understanding reality during task analysis. Collecting all the necessary information for the solution and analyzing it is carried out independently by the client with the help of a coach. For this, special techniques are used, one of the main types of which is coaching technology.

Research object and used methods

Analysis of scientific literature, theoretical-comparative analysis, questionnaire surveys, analysis of regulatory and legal documents, observation, interview, sociometry, mathematical-statistical summarization of experiment-test results were used.

The obtained results and their analysis

The main principle of coaching is that each person (team) can find the most optimal ways to achieve goals and can choose the way to move towards it. These principles apply to everyone.

The main principles of coaching are based on:

- all people have the ability to develop;
- people are able to change only when they want to and are ready for it;
- our confidence in our potential is directly related to success;
- how we define success directly affects our achievements;
- we limit our potential by our beliefs (for example, believing that certain things cannot be done due to external or situational barriers);
- people learn only if they really participate in this process;
- we can learn through anything, but learning only happens when we think and plan for the future;
- In order to help others, we must always develop ourselves [1].

Coaching helps to solve many problems in different areas of life and activity to different people and in different ways. How wide this range is can be understood from the classification of coaching types. Thus, in the most general form, coaching is divided into two types:

1. In professional activities, where it is possible to consider issues related to almost any profession and type of activity;

2. In a non-professional field where issues of family, marriage, interpersonal relations, etc. are considered.

According to the number of clients, coaching is divided into the following types:

1. Individual (personal, private);
2. Group (team, corporate).

The duration of coaching depends on the client's goals. If it's a simple single task, this can be achieved in one session, but may take months. The duration of one coaching session varies from 45 minutes to one and a half hours and is carried out according to approximately the same scenario (except for introductory and final sessions) [1].

Summarizing the results of previous training in coaching (what was achieved, what was not).

- Looking for solutions to things that cannot be done.
- Setting a goal for the current session.
- Working on special questions for this training on one of the coaching technologies.
- Summarizing the time until the next training session and making a work plan.

In the process of research, the following principles were identified in the organization of coaching:

1. First, everything is good in all people.

Often we think of ourselves, our actions, or other people as "abnormal, weirder." And that's why we don't want to work on ourselves, or we refuse to understand another person, to establish a relationship with him [1].

However, according to this principle, we are all normal. And you should not justify life's difficulties and failures with conclusions drawn from childhood traumas or bitter life experiences. The same principle applies to other people - everything is fine with them, it's just that we can't understand them now or we don't want to understand them.

2. Second, you already have EVERYTHING you need to achieve your goals.

Everyone (including you) has all the necessary resources, both external (money, connections, people and other material and informational resources) and internal (experience, knowledge, skills, talent). Knowing this principle will allow you to eliminate all possible "reasons" why you cannot become what you want right now, and will also help you achieve your goals and be happy here and now.

3. Third, we always make the best choice.

Looking back, we can see many actions and decisions made by us. Often we judge these actions and decisions as wrong. However, it is important to recognize that whatever decision we make is the best for us in that situation and at that time. Therefore, no one should judge or be judged. According to the third principle, we draw conclusions and move forward without guilt or resentment.

4. Fourth, all people make the best choices available to them and act with positive intentions.

Human nature is such that the purpose of any action is to seek something good for oneself. Thus, people's actions, even those that harm others, do not initially have a negative charge. The fact is that people do not always choose an environmentally friendly way to achieve their goals. But understanding this will allow you to better understand the reason for a person's actions and find a common language with him.

5. Fifth, there will always be changes and they are inevitable.

This principle says that we should not resist any changes, because they are inevitable and contribute to our progress. Everything changes and so do we. Another question - in which direction?

In general, we always have a choice:

1. Or up - for happiness, success, love, development of one's talents, for the benefit of other people and the universe

2. Or down - suffering, anger, anger, illness, loneliness.

"Confidentiality" norm. Information about the life of someone, more precisely, a participant in the group, expressed during the coaching process, the expression of thoughts, feelings, getting into uncomfortable situations during the performance of games and exercises should not be outside the scope of coaching. The deviation of such information from the training limits can cause him various unexpected unpleasantness. There are two functional connections in human behavior: stimulation and regulation. Mental processes, phenomena and intuition, perception, memory, imagination, attention, thinking, ability, temperament, character, emotions - all of these mainly provide regulation of behavior. As for its stimulation or motivation, it is related to the concepts of motivation and motivation. These concepts include a person's needs, interests, purpose, intentions, aspirations, motivations, external factors that cause it to behave in a certain way, includes ideas about managing any activity in the process of its implementation [3,4,5].

Reason - a reason occurs in the system of human needs and in this from the conscious variable levels to their interests. During the implementation of behavioral actions, dynamically formed motivations can be changed (changed) at all stages of the action, and the behavior often ends with a changed motivation rather than the initial one. The reason has a complex internal structure: when the need arises, the need for something is accompanied by emotional anxiety, dissatisfaction, the reason begins;

The idea of motivation arises when trying to explain, not describe, behavior. This is "Why?", "For what purpose?" Searching for answers to questions such as "why?", "what does ...?". Determining and describing the causes of persistent changes in behavior is the answer to the question of the motivation of the actions that contain it. Any behavior can be explained by internal and external reasons.

In the first case, the psychological characteristics of the subject of behavior are the starting and ending points of the explanation, and in the second case, the external conditions of its activity.

In the first case, they talk about motives, needs, goals, intentions, desires, interests, etc., and in the second - about benefits arising from the current situation. Sometimes all the psychological factors that arise from within a person determine his behavior. Then they talk about dispositional and situational motivation as analogs of intrinsic and extrinsic behavioral determination [2]. Dispositional and situational motivation are not independent. Dispositions can be updated under the influence of a certain situation, and vice versa, the activation of certain dispositions (reasons, needs) leads to a change in the situation, or rather, its perception by the subject. Immediately, the corresponding behavior of a person should not be considered as a reaction to certain internal or external stimuli, but the result of continuous interaction of his state with the situation should be taken into account. It involves viewing motivation as a cyclical

process of constant interaction and change, in which the object of action and the situation interact and the result is actual observable behavior. will be [4]

Motivation serves as a continuous selection and decision-making process based on consideration of behavioral alternatives.

Motivation explains the direction of actions, the organization and stability of integrated activities aimed at achieving a specific goal. Action, in contrast to motivation, belongs to the subject of behavior - it is a permanent personal property, an internal urge to perform certain actions. Motive can also be defined as a concept that represents many dispositions in a generalized form.

The second concept after need in the sense of motivation is purpose.

A goal is called a direct conscious result, it is directed to actions related to activities that satisfy a real need at the moment.

Disposition (motives), needs and goals are the main components of a person's motivational field.

The motivational field of a person can be evaluated from the point of view of its development according to the following parameters: breadth, flexibility and hierarchization [4].

The breadth of the motivational field means the variety of motivational factors presented at each level - diversity (motives), needs and goals. When a person has different motives, needs and goals, his motivational field is more developed.

Flexibility. Such a motivational field is considered more flexible, in which various lower-level motivational motivators can be used to satisfy motivational motivation of a more general nature (higher level). For example, a person's motivation field is more flexible, and depending on the conditions of satisfaction of the same motive, he can use more different means than another person. One person's need for knowledge can be satisfied only by television, radio and cinema, and for another, various books, periodicals, communication with people are also a means of satisfying it. In the latter, the field of motivation is more flexible.

Hierarchization is a characteristic feature of the structure of each of the levels of organization of the motivational sphere taken separately. Some thoughts (motives, goals) appear stronger and more often than others; others are weak and less frequently updated. The greater the differences in the strength and frequency of actualization of motivational forms at a certain level, the higher the hierarchy of the motivational field [3].

In addition to motives, needs and goals, interests, tasks, desires and intentions are also considered as stimulators of human behavior.

Interest means a special motivational state of a cognitive nature, which is usually not directly related to any need that exists at a certain time. Interests fall into a special type of activity called preliminary research. As a motivational factor based on a specific situation, a task occurs when the body encounters an obstacle that must be overcome in order to move forward during a movement aimed at achieving a specific goal. Desires and intentions appear instantaneously and are often variable motivational subjective states that correspond to changing conditions for action. Although interests, tasks, desires and intentions are included in the system of motivational factors, they are involved in motivating behavior, but they do not motivate to the extent that they play a role in it. They are more responsible for the style than for the course of action.

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